

IODINE DEFICIENCY AND ITS HEALTH IMPACT: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF GLOBAL AND INDIAN PERSPECTIVES

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ABSTRACT

Iodine deficiency disorders (IDD) remain a significant public health challenge worldwide, despite decades of progress in prevention through universal salt iodization. Globally, inadequate iodine intake continues to affect populations in both developed and developing countries, contributing to a spectrum of health consequences, most notably goitre, hypothyroidism, impaired neurodevelopment, and increased risk of stillbirth and infant mortality. The most critical impact is on cognitive development, as iodine deficiency during pregnancy and early childhood can result in irreversible intellectual impairments, reducing educational attainment and economic productivity at a population level. International surveillance data indicate notable regional disparities: while high-income countries have largely eliminated IDD through salt iodization and monitoring programs, many low- and middle-income countries, particularly

in parts of Africa and South Asia, still report insufficient iodine coverage. Therefore, it is crucial to address the challenges particularly the challenges for eliminating goitre and hypothyroidism but also to safeguarding cognitive development and population health, thereby enhancing human capital and long-term socioeconomic growth.

KEYWORDS: Iodine deficiency disorders, Goitre, Hypothyroidism, Impaired neurodevelopment, Socioeconomic growth.

1. INTRODUCTION

Iodine is one of the important trace elements essential for the synthesis of thyroid hormones, thyroxine (T4) and triiodothyronine (T3), which regulate the key physiological processes including metabolism, growth, and neurodevelopment. It has been known that the human body does not synthesize iodine, making dietary intake critical for health. The average adult requires about 150 micrograms of iodine per day, with higher requirements during the pregnancy and lactation stages in women due to increased demands and losses at pre- and post-delivery condition (Dafnis and Sabatini, 1999).

Despite of advancements in prevention strategies such as universal salt iodization, iodine deficiency remains a major global health issue, affecting millions of people worldwide. As per literature survey, approximately 1.88 billion people of worldwide, particularly from iodine limited places are at risk of iodine deficiency. Most of the cases are from vulnerable populations in Africa and South-East Asia, particularly among children and pregnant women (Businge et al., 2021; Businge et al., 2022). Iodine deficiency in these countries is influenced by variety of interconnected factors such as- limited access to iodine-rich foods, inadequate healthcare infrastructure and monitoring and funding issues, etc. are some major reasons in African and developing Asian countries.

However, some of the historical landmarks in iodine research, including the identification of goitre-endemic regions and the discovery of the critical relationship between iodine and thyroid gland function, laid the essential foundation for contemporary public health interventions (Zimmermann, 2009). Early observations linked areas with endemic goitre to iodine-deficient soils and diets, which highlighted the environmental and nutritional roots of the condition. Subsequently, researchers established that iodine is a key component in the synthesis of thyroid hormones, which regulate metabolism, growth, and brain development. This understanding propelled the development of targeted iodine supplementation strategies, such as iodized salt programs, which have become central to preventing iodine deficiency disorders globally. These landmark findings not only advanced scientific knowledge but also shaped effective policies and interventions to improve population health and reduce the burden of iodine deficiency-related diseases worldwide (Chyngyshpaeva et al., 2024).

The seriousness of iodine deficiency ranges from mild cognitive impairments to severe neurological damage which elevated the mortality rates among infants and mothers. Such health consequences are collectively classified as Iodine Deficiency Disorders (IDDs), which

include conditions such as goitre, hypothyroidism, and various neurological and developmental impairments. The significance of this public health issue led to the implementation of major initiatives like the Universal Salt Iodization (USI) program, which has resulted in substantial progress in reducing IDD, though complete elimination has yet to be achieved (Kissock, et al., 2024; Vargas-Uricoechea et al., 2019).

2. Essential Function of Iodine in Human Health

Iodine the essential component of thyroid hormones which regulate several metabolic and developmental pathways:

- **Neurodevelopment:** Thyroid hormones are essential for normal brain maturation, especially during foetal development and early infancy. Insufficient maternal iodine intake disrupts foetal brain development and can lead to permanent intellectual and motor impairments (Godbole et al., 2023; Rees and Brough, 2025).
- **Metabolism Regulation:** Thyroid hormones play a key role in maintaining the basal metabolic rate, regulating thermogenesis, and modulating the lipid, carbohydrate, and protein metabolism. When these hormones are deficient, the disruption of these pathways results in hypothyroidism, often accompanied by weight gain, cold intolerance, dyslipidemia, and other metabolic dysfunctions.
- **Growth:** Continuous iodine intake during childhood is essential to support proper skeletal growth and neurological development. However, inadequate intake over extended periods interferes with thyroid hormone production, which may result in stunted linear growth, delayed bone age, cognitive and motor impairments, and, in severe cases, irreversible developmental deficits.
- **Reproductive Health:** Iodine plays a crucial role in reproductive health by influencing fertility, menstrual cycle regulation, and pregnancy outcomes. In adults, both iodine deficiency and excess can disrupt thyroid hormone homeostasis, leading to hypothyroidism or hyperthyroidism. Such imbalances may impair ovarian function, cause menstrual irregularities, and negatively affect embryo implantation and fetal development. In men, abnormal iodine status can reduce sperm quality, motility, and overall reproductive potential, thereby further contributing to infertility (Partal-Lorente et al., 2017).

Since the human body is unable to store substantial reserves of iodine, a regular and sufficient dietary intake is required to sustain thyroid hormone balance. Primary nutritional sources of

iodine include iodized salt, dairy products, seafood, and some cereal grains. However, the availability of iodine-rich foods varies across regions, largely depending on agricultural practices, soil iodine content, and dietary habits, which together influence the risk of iodine deficiency in different populations (Hatch-McChesney and Lieberman, 2022).

3. EPIDEMIOLOGY OF IODINE DEFICIENCY

3.1. Global Prevalence and Distribution

Although remarkable progress has been achieved over the past few decades, iodine deficiency continues to pose a significant global public health concern. As of 2019, an estimated 81.4 million women of reproductive age were affected worldwide, reflecting the persistent vulnerability of this high-risk group. The burden of iodine deficiency is disproportionately concentrated in Central Sub-Saharan Africa, South Asia, and select regions of Eastern Europe, where dietary patterns, limited access to iodized salt, and environmental factors such as iodine-deficient soils exacerbate the problem. Encouragingly, global trends show improvement: since 1990, the age-standardized point prevalence has declined by approximately 13.3%. The most substantial reductions have been documented in Southeast Asia and North Africa, a success largely attributed to widespread implementation of Universal Salt Iodization (USI) programs and strengthened public health interventions. Nevertheless, the uneven pace of progress across regions highlights the need for sustained efforts, robust monitoring systems, and targeted strategies to reach underserved populations and achieve global iodine sufficiency (Kissock, et al., 2024).

At the global level, median urinary iodine concentration (UIC) serves as the primary biomarker for assessing the iodine status of populations, as it reliably reflects recent iodine intake. To address widespread deficiencies, more than 145 countries have adopted salt iodization programs as a cornerstone of public health strategy. Currently, it is estimated that approximately 70% of households worldwide have access to adequately iodized salt, representing a major achievement in nutritional intervention. However, despite this progress, significant disparities persist. Several countries—particularly those with remote, rural, or economically disadvantaged populations—remain vulnerable due to inadequate program implementation, gaps in distribution systems, weak regulatory monitoring, and reliance on locally produced non-iodized salt. These challenges highlight the importance of sustaining universal salt iodization efforts while simultaneously strengthening surveillance, public

awareness campaigns, and targeted support for at-risk regions (Rah et al., 2015; Kissock, et al., 2024).

3.2. Iodine Nutrition Status in India

India continues to carry a disproportionately high burden of iodine deficiency, which remains a major public health concern despite decades of intervention. A key underlying factor is the widespread iodine deficiency in the soil across much of the Indian subcontinent, which in turn reduces the iodine content of locally cultivated crops and dietary staples consumed by the population (Kaur et al., 2017; Krishna et al., 2022). As a result, Iodine Deficiency Disorders (IDDs) are endemic in several geographic zones, particularly in the sub-Himalayan belt, the Indo-Gangetic plains, and certain other vulnerable pockets where populations heavily depend on locally sourced food (Krishna et al., 2022). National surveys consistently highlight the magnitude of the problem, with an estimated 350 million Indians still at risk of inadequate iodine intake. The regional impact is further reflected in global patterns—over half of the world's children with insufficient iodine intake reside in South and South-East Asia, underscoring the urgent need for sustained and comprehensive efforts in India to address this persistent challenge (Kaur et al., 2017).

The National Iodine Deficiency Disorders Control Programme (NIDDCP), launched in India alongside subsequent public health interventions such as universal salt iodization, periodic monitoring, and awareness campaigns, has significantly contributed to a decline in the total goitre rate (TGR) among children across several states. These successes highlight the impact of sustained iodine supplementation strategies and the critical role of government-led initiatives in improving population-level iodine status. However, notable disparities remain. States such as Maharashtra and West Bengal continue to report comparatively higher goitre prevalence, indicating uneven progress in achieving adequate iodine nutrition nationwide (Chandra et al., 2006). These variations can be attributed to inconsistent implementation of iodization programs, disparities in salt production and distribution networks, weak regulatory oversight, and insufficient surveillance mechanisms. The persistence of higher goitre rates in some regions underscores the need for region-specific strategies, stronger program monitoring, and revitalization of public health efforts to ensure uniform progress across the country.

4. HEALTH CONSEQUENCES OF IODINE DEFICIENCY

4.1. Goitre

Goitre, or enlargement of the thyroid gland, represents the most recognizable and visible manifestation of iodine deficiency and remains a key indicator of population-level iodine status. The condition arises as a compensatory response to reduced thyroid hormone synthesis caused by inadequate iodine intake. In this state, the thyroid gland undergoes hyperplasia and hypertrophy of its follicular cells in an effort to increase its capacity to trap and utilize the limited iodine available in circulation. While this adaptive mechanism initially helps maintain near-normal hormone levels, persistent iodine deficiency leads to progressive thyroid enlargement. Over time, goitres may become nodular, cosmetically disfiguring, and symptomatic. In advanced cases, an enlarged thyroid can cause compressive symptoms such as difficulty swallowing, hoarseness, and even airway obstruction due to tracheal compression. Goitre is observed across all age groups but disproportionately affects school-aged children and women of reproductive age, groups that are particularly vulnerable to the consequences of iodine deficiency. Beyond cosmetic and mechanical complications, the presence of goitre reflects a deeper burden of iodine deficiency in the community, often serving as a marker of underlying functional thyroid impairment.^{[5][12]}

4.2. Neurological and Developmental Disorders

Iodine plays a pivotal role in neurodevelopment, and deficiencies during pregnancy or early childhood can lead to serious adverse outcomes:

- **Cretinism:** The most devastating outcome of severe and prolonged iodine deficiency is cretinism, a condition marked by irreversible intellectual disability, deaf-mutism, and significant motor dysfunction. Affected individuals also exhibit stunted physical growth, delayed skeletal maturation, and characteristic facial features, including a broad nose, thickened tongue, and coarse skin. These clinical manifestations reflect the critical role of thyroid hormones in both brain and physical development during fetal and early postnatal life (Bernal and Nunez, 2000; Salisbury, 2003; Kapil, 2007; Verheesen and Schweitzer, 2008).
- **Cognitive Impairment:** Even relatively mild-to-moderate iodine deficiency during pregnancy exerts measurable effects on fetal brain development, resulting in a population-wide reduction in average IQ by an estimated 10–15 points. Such cognitive impairment translates into lower educational performance, reduced learning capacity, and diminished

workplace productivity, thereby imposing both individual and societal costs (Bailote et al., 2012).

- **Learning Disabilities:** Affected children often present with a spectrum of neurodevelopmental impairments including attention deficits, delayed acquisition of motor milestones such as sitting, standing, and walking, as well as language delays. These deficits translate into poor cognitive function, reduced memory and concentration, and consequently lower academic performance compared to their peers. Over time, such impairments limit learning potential, hinder educational achievement, and may contribute to decreased self-esteem and social interaction difficulties. The cumulative effect is not only detrimental to the child's personal development but also places an added burden on families, schools, and society at large.
- **Brain Structure Changes:** Experimental research demonstrates that iodine deficiency exerts profound effects on the developing brain, including impaired hippocampal growth, defective myelination of neuronal pathways, and altered patterns of neurotransmitter expression, all of which contribute to long-term cognitive and behavioral deficits (Redman et al., 2016).

4.3. Maternal and Neonatal Outcomes

Iodine-deficient mothers are at substantially higher risk of pregnancy complications, including miscarriage, stillbirth, preterm delivery, and congenital abnormalities such as cretinism and congenital hypothyroidism. This is because insufficient iodine impairs maternal thyroid hormone production, which is essential for regulating fetal brain and skeletal development during early gestation. Infants born to such mothers frequently present with low birth weight, reduced head circumference, and biochemical or clinical hypothyroidism. These conditions place neonates at risk of delayed physical growth, impaired motor coordination, and reduced cognitive function. Over time, these developmental delays can translate into long-term learning difficulties, decreased educational performance, and diminished productivity in adulthood (Gargari et al., 2014).

4.4. Hypothyroidism

Chronic iodine deficiency results in hypothyroidism, which presents with symptoms such as fatigue, weight gain, cold intolerance, constipation, and depression. In children, it further contributes to growth retardation and impaired neurological development (Zimmermann and Boelaert, 2015).

4.5. Impaired Immunity and Socioeconomic Impact

Iodine deficiency compromises immune function, increasing vulnerability to infections. At the population level, reduced cognitive capacity translates into lower productivity, persistent poverty, and impeded national development (Biban and Lichiardopol, 20117).

5. ASSESSMENT AND DIAGNOSIS

- Urinary Iodine Excretion (UIE): Median urinary iodine concentration is the most reliable marker of recent population iodine intake, with values below 100 µg/L in non-pregnant individuals indicating deficiency.
- Serum Thyroglobulin and Thyroid Stimulating Hormone (TSH): Elevated levels of TSH and thyroglobulin are characteristic findings in iodine deficiency, particularly in neonates.
- Total Goitre Rate (TGR): Goitre prevalence clinically assesses the proportion of a population with thyroid enlargement and serves as an indicator of long-term, rather than acute, iodine deficiency.
- Neonatal Screening: Early detection of congenital hypothyroidism using dried blood spot TSH screening is a critical intervention for newborns.

Epidemiological surveillance using indicators such as urinary iodine concentration, neonatal TSH levels, thyroglobulin measurements, and goitre prevalence plays a crucial role in monitoring the iodine status of populations

6. PREVENTION AND CONTROL STRATEGIES OF IODINE DEFICIENCY

6.1. Universal Salt Iodization (USI)

Universal Salt Iodization (USI) is widely recognized as the most cost-effective and sustainable public health intervention for the prevention and control of iodine deficiency disorders (IDD), and it has been strongly endorsed by both WHO and UNICEF. The process involves the sustained fortification of edible salt with potassium iodate, thereby guaranteeing a simple, affordable, and equitable means of delivering adequate iodine intake across entire populations (Gorstein et al., 2020). The success of USI is evident globally, with reports indicating a nearly 76% reduction in goitre prevalence and substantial improvements in cognitive outcomes among children. Over the past decades, remarkable progress has been achieved in policy adoption: more than 120 countries have introduced national salt iodization programs, and at least 97 of these have integrated enforcement mechanisms through legislation or regulation (Rah et al. 2015). These achievements highlight USI as a cornerstone

of nutritional policy and a critical tool in safeguarding both health and socioeconomic development worldwide."

6.2. Dietary Diversification

- Iodine-rich foods form the primary dietary sources for maintaining adequate iodine status in populations. Among these, seafood such as fish, shellfish, and seaweed are particularly rich sources, as marine organisms naturally concentrate iodine from seawater. Dairy products, including milk, yogurt, and cheese, contribute substantially to iodine intake in many regions, though their content may vary depending on farming practices and animal feed. Eggs also provide moderate amounts of iodine, making them a valuable addition to the diet, especially for populations with limited access to seafood. In several countries, staple foods such as salt and certain grains are fortified with iodine to ensure widespread and equitable intake, thereby compensating for natural dietary insufficiencies.
- Public health education plays a pivotal role in preventing iodine deficiency by promoting awareness of dietary practices that ensure adequate iodine intake. Campaigns emphasize the importance of consuming balanced and diversified diets that naturally include iodine-rich foods such as seafood, dairy products, and eggs, while also highlighting the need to consistently use iodized salt in household cooking. Community-based programs and school initiatives often target vulnerable groups, particularly women of reproductive age, pregnant mothers, and children, stressing iodine's critical role in brain development and overall health. Educational interventions also aim to correct misconceptions, such as the belief that sea salt or rock salt provides equivalent.
- Regional considerations: In landlocked and mountainous regions, where access to marine foods is limited and natural iodine levels in soil and water are typically low, populations are at particularly high risk of iodine deficiency. In such settings, reliance on dietary sources alone is insufficient to meet daily iodine requirements, making fortification and supplementation programs indispensable public health strategies (Wu et al. 2024).

6.3. Supplementation Programs

- In contexts where iodized salt is not readily available, or during humanitarian emergencies that disrupt regular food supplies, iodine supplementation in the form of iodized oil or tablets is provided to vulnerable populations. These supplements serve as an effective short- to medium-term strategy to prevent iodine deficiency, particularly among

groups with high physiological needs, such as pregnant women, lactating mothers, and young children.

- Targeted interventions are specifically designed to address the needs of high-risk groups, including pregnant and lactating women, infants and young children, and communities living in remote or disadvantaged regions. These groups are prioritized because of their heightened physiological iodine requirements and their increased vulnerability to the adverse effects of deficiency (Yadav and Pandav, 2018).

7. POLICY MEASURES AND PUBLIC HEALTH IMPLICATIONS

- **Monitoring and Evaluation:** Regular surveillance ensures that iodized salt effectively reaches target populations while preventing excessive intake that may harm health.
- **Education Campaigns:** Public awareness campaigns address misconceptions about iodized salt and promote its sustained use.
- **Integration with Health Programs:** Prevention of iodine deficiency disorders (IDD) is increasingly integrated with maternal and child health initiatives, enhancing efficiency and maximizing resource utilization (Li and Eastman, 2012).
- **Legislation and Regulation:** Legal mandates for salt iodization, coupled with stringent quality assurance across the production chain, are essential for sustaining supply and ensuring population-wide coverage (Yadav et al. 2013).

Collaboration among governments, industry, civil society, and international organizations is essential to sustain progress and address challenges such as resistance to fortification and changing salt-consumption patterns.

8. Challenges and Research Directions

- Ensuring the consistent quality and equitable distribution of iodized salt, especially within informal markets and remote communities.
- Reaching marginalized populations: Migrant, nomadic, and disaster-affected populations frequently face restricted access to fortified foods.
- Measuring and mitigating excess: Monitoring iodine intake is essential to prevent excess exposure, particularly in regions with naturally high iodine levels or in settings prone to over-iodization (Kapil, 2018).
- Innovations in delivery: Current research directions include exploring new food vehicles for fortification beyond salt—such as flour, rice, or condiments—and designing novel

supplementation strategies tailored to the needs of vulnerable groups and hard-to-reach populations.

- Advancing research: Key research priorities include improving biomarkers of iodine status, examining the cognitive impacts of mild to moderate deficiency, and clarifying the molecular pathways responsible for neurological outcomes (Hatch-McChesney and Lieberman, 2022; Lisco et al. 2023).

9. CONCLUSION

Although substantial progress has been made in the control of iodine deficiency disorders (IDD), the condition continues to pose a significant public health concern, particularly among vulnerable and underserved populations. Universal salt iodization remains a model example of a cost-effective, scalable, and sustainable nutrition intervention. Nonetheless, sustained progress depends on the implementation of robust policy frameworks, regular and systematic monitoring, cross-sectoral collaboration, and ongoing public education to reinforce awareness and compliance. Confronting both persistent gaps in coverage and emerging challenges, such as dietary shifts and inequities in access, is essential for achieving the full elimination of iodine deficiency. Ultimately, these efforts are critical not only for protecting present populations but also for securing optimal health, cognitive potential, and socioeconomic development for future generations.

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